

Decarbonization with economic growth and job creation

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Standfirst

An ensemble of green industrial policies and targeted subsidies, coupled with a mild carbon tax, is the most promising strategy to support an orderly transition towards achieving the Paris Agreement targets. Such a policy package can be designed to have a neutral effect on public finances and boost job creation, while preserving economic stability and income growth.

Messages for policy

- Green industrial policies should be implemented to achieve rapid decarbonization while maintaining high employment and macro-financial stability.
- Combining energy and industry regulations with subsidies for green R&D and renewable deployment ensures rapid and orderly mitigation.
- Carbon taxes should be mild, mostly enabling green public spending, discouraging fossil investments, and accelerating renewable deployment, especially when tax rates are higher in hard-to-abate sectors.
- Sectors with long investment cycles (such as heavy industry) should be targeted early to prevent decarbonization bottlenecks and the lock-in of carbon-intensive assets, even if initial costs are higher.

The policy problem

Rapid and substantial cuts in greenhouse gas emissions are essential to avoid dangerous climate change, yet the transition to a low-carbon economy risks being either too slow or too abrupt, with severe socio-economic costs. Policymakers must therefore design measures that strike a balance between rapid decarbonization and preserving economic stability, but combining these tools into a socioeconomically favourable policy remains understudied.

The findings

Green industrial policies (command-and-control policies and targeted subsidies) can rapidly cut emissions and boost employment, while maintain macro-financial stability and preserve economic growth. When such policies are combined with a mild sector-specific carbon tax, they can also balance the public budget. This is a cost-effective policy package and promotes an orderly transition to achieve a below-2°C pathway with fiscal costs under 1.5% of GDP per year. Coupling bans on fossil fuel plant construction with the introduction of electrification standards forms the core of top-performing climate policies. Clear green regulatory targets lower policy uncertainty and steer technological change without raising firms' energy costs.

The study

We applied an agent-based integrated assessment model (DSK) model [1] to assess the effects of diverse global decarbonization policies on production, employment, and macro-financial stability from 2022 to 2160.

Source Research

Wieners, C., Lamperti, F., Dosi, G. and Roventini, R. (2025). Policies for rapid decarbonization with steady economic transition and employment creation. *Nature Sustainability*, XXX.

Further reading

Lamperti, F., Bosetti V., Roventini, A. & Tavoni, M. The public costs of climate-induced financial instability, *Nature Climate Change*, 9, 829-833.

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This paper introduces an extension of the DSK model that enables investigation into the macro-financial implications of global warming and compliments the present analysis by focusing on climate impacts beyond transition risks.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.